

An All-Dielectric, 3-Axis Electric Field Sensor Using Quasi-Longitudinally Configured Electro-Optic Crystals

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Abstract—We describe a stabilized, all-dielectric, 3-axis electric field sensor using electro-optic (EO) crystals. By directing the laser probe quasi-longitudinally with respect to the optic axis of the crystal, we have improved stability by three orders of magnitude and substantially reduced phase noise. While the modulation depth of the output signal is slightly reduced, overall sensitivity is greatly improved due to the larger signal to noise ratio. Unlike conventional EO sensors, measurements can be made with 50 meters of optical fibers without excessive noise. Additionally, the sensor and fibers can be moved during measurements without the need for compensation optics or recalibration. This makes the sensor very practical for actual field test applications and attractive for potential commercial use.

I. INTRODUCTION

We have developed a three-axis, electro-optic sensor (EOS) for noninvasive measurements of electric fields [1,2]. Conventional field probes such as dipole antennas are metallic-based, causing unwanted field perturbations and reflections which inhibit their use in enclosed structures, high power microwaves (HPM) and large magnetic fields [3]. An EOS is all-dielectric, has a large bandwidth ($> 10\text{GHz}$), and can be used in fields up to 10^6 V/m . Additionally, because of its small size (5mm in diameter) the EOS is ideal for measuring fields inside small cavities and tight spaces. But in spite of these well-known advantages, EO sensors are rarely used in actual field tests, have low commercial appeal, and are usually confined to more research-oriented laboratory applications. The primary reason for this is optical phase noise, which causes instabilities and reduced sensitivity. As a result, the EOS can only be used with short and secured lengths of optical fiber, making it impractical for many applications. In this paper we present a modified EOS sensor design that virtually eliminates this problem, making the sensor more attractive for commercial use.

II. LIMITATIONS OF CONVENTIONAL EO SENSORS

An example of the noise acquired by a conventional EOS when its optical fibers are extended in length is shown by the

Fig. 1: Output signals from an EOS under a pulsed E-field, (a): Conventional EOS with 1.5 meters of optical fiber, (b) Sensor in (a) with 50m fiber optic patch cords, (c) QLMEOS with 1.5 meter fibers, (d) Sensor in (c) with 50m fiber optic patch cords.

oscilloscope traces in Figures 1(a) and 1(b). The (upper) yellow traces represent the optical modulation signal from the sensor placed in a pulsed electric field (lower green trace). The time delay in the sensor signal of Fig. 1(b) is due to the transit time of the laser through an additional 50m of fiber optic patch cord. More importantly, it can be seen that the additional optical fiber introduces excessive noise which severely impacts the signal to noise ratio (SNR) and sensitivity of the EOS. Using various lengths of optical patch cords, we found that the noise level increases linearly with the fiber length. In many applications, such as HPM, optical fibers that are 50 meters or longer are necessary in order to isolate the readout instrumentation from the source of RF power. Thus the noise shown in Figure 1(b) makes the EOS very impractical and presents difficulties in utilizing it outside of the laboratory.

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Fig. 2: (a) Balanced photoreceiver circuit for noise cancellation, (b): orthogonal polarization components of optical signal, revealing a polarization dependence and phase origin of the noise.

While some optical amplitude noise is generated at the connection points between the sensor fibers and the optical patch cords, the majority of the acquired noise in Fig. 1(b) originated in the phase of the optical signal. This was determined by examining the noise in orthogonal polarization components of the light beam, using a polarization beam splitter (PBS) and the balanced photoreceiver configuration shown in Figure 2(a). At the photocurrent balance point ($\Delta i = 0$), the noise signals in the two polarization components (trace 1 and 2 in Fig. 2(b)) exhibited equal and opposite amplitudes, indicating their polarization dependence and phase origin. Therefore subtracting the two components (a common noise cancellation technique) only doubles the phase noise level rather than eliminates it. But since the EO modulation is also polarization dependent and doubled by the signal subtraction, the overall SNR remains more or less unchanged.

Optical phase noise is mainly due to distributions of birefringence, which occur intrinsically (within the crystal) as well as externally (within the optical fibers). In a typical EOS (e.g., based on LiNbO_3 or LiTaO_3), the laser beam is passed along a crystalline direction of maximum birefringence (i.e., perpendicular to the optic axis). This is done to exploit the largest EO coefficient of the crystal and maximize its modulating power. Unfortunately, this also maximizes the phase noise produced by the crystal and makes the EOS very sensitive to movements and vibrations. The phase noise produced by the crystal usually occurs at very low

frequencies and is responsible for instabilities and drifts in calibration, rather than the type of high frequency noise shown in Fig. 1(b). Stabilizing the EOS requires cumbersome compensation optics (or polarization controllers) that continuously adjust to correct the state of polarization as the phase drifts. To keep the sensor head small in size and free of metallic components, the compensation optics must be placed at the end of the sensor's output fiber, which must be polarization maintaining (PM). Because PM fiber is birefringent, it adds additional phase to the optical signal. Consequently, additional low frequency noise will be present due to movement or vibrations of the fiber as well. This presents difficulties when the EOS is used for outdoor testing with very long fibers (e.g., 50m). In such cases, the low frequency noise associated with wind and vibration can become excessive and overburden the compensation optics, making the EOS unstable and its calibration unreliable. Thus short and secured lengths of optical fibers must be used in this sensor configuration.

The spectral bandwidth of the laser is another source of phase noise, and is likely to be the cause of the higher frequency noise in Fig. 1(b). Distributions of laser wavelength (\sim GHz) are directly converted to distributions of phase as the laser passes through the birefringent PM output fiber. Since phase is generally proportional to optical path length, the noise level increases linearly with the length of optical fiber. Because spectral phase noise occurs at such high frequencies, it cannot be eliminated with compensation optics (which can only handle low frequency noise). Thus, as with the low frequency phase noise, shorter optical fibers are necessary for reliable operation and optimal SNR.

III. QUASI-LONGITUDINAL MODE EO SENSOR

The requirement of short and secured optical fibers with the conventional EOS presents difficulties for field testing and commercial applications of the EOS. An alternative is the quasi-longitudinal mode EOS (QLMEOS) shown in Fig. 3. In the QLMEOS, the optical path of the laser makes a very small angle with respect to the optic axis of the EO crystal. This quasi-longitudinal path produces a small phase shift in the beam (similar to a retardation plate), which enhances the modulation signal. Because of the low birefringence along this optical path, crystal-induced phase drift is reduced by over three orders of magnitude, compared to the conventional EOS [2]. Compensation optics are no longer required and the analyzer (polarizer) can be integrated into the sensor head, rather than placed at the end of the output fiber. Since the optical signal is analyzed within the sensor head, the vibrational and spectral phase noise associated with the PM output fiber is virtually eliminated. SNR is greatly improved and the optical fibers can be extended to over 50 meters with negligible noise added to the modulation signal. An example of this improvement is shown in Figs 1(c) and 1(d), where our conventional EOS from Figs. 1(a) and (b) was replaced with the QLMEOS. It can be seen that the SNR was essentially unchanged when 50 meters of optical patch cord

Fig. 3: (a) Ruggedized QLMEOS attached to 50m fiber reel, (b) Close-up of a 3-axis QLMEOS sensor head, (c) miniaturized QLMEOS for measuring fields inside small cavities

was added. We have implemented the QLMEOS configuration with EO crystals of Lithium Niobate (LiNbO_3) and Potassium Dideuterium Phosphate (KD^*P). In both cases, the intrinsic modulating power of the crystal is actually *less* than that of the conventional EOS due to a smaller value of $n^3 r_{ij}$. Here n is the refractive index of the crystal and r_{ij} is its Pockels coefficient. Despite this reduction in modulating power, overall sensitivity is greatly improved due to a lower noise level and larger signal amplitude. We obtain a larger signal amplitude (in spite of a reduced modulation depth) due to a several-fold improvement in the optical coupling between input and output fibers. This is achieved by means of a larger core multimode (MM) output fiber, which can be used in place of the PM fiber since beam analysis has already taken place in the sensor head and polarization preservation is no longer necessary. Typically, three to five times more optical power is collected with a MM fiber, which is directly carried over to the signal amplitude. Finally, compared to the conventional EOS, the QLMEOS is more cost effective since it eliminates the need for expensive polarization controllers and the PM fibers for the output signal.

IV. OPERATION OF QLMEOS

Because of the absence of compensation optics, set-up and operation of the QLMEOS is simplified. Optical components (polarizers, lenses, etc) are in fixed positions within the sensor head, and do not require adjustments or modifications. As indicated by Fig 3(a), connection points between QLMEOS and external instrumentation are made with an

Fig. 4: Field Testing of QLMEOS using numerous RF sources

optical input fiber (connected to a laser) and an optical output fiber (connected to a photoreceiver). The photoreceiver converts the optical signal into an electrical (RF) voltage signal V_{RF} which is measured by a readout instrument such as an oscilloscope or spectrum analyzer. Photoreceivers also supply a DC monitor voltage V_{DC} that must be used in conjunction with V_{RF} to obtain the modulation depth $m = V_{RF}/V_{DC}$. The external field E is obtained through the simple expression $E = cm$, where c is conversion factor that depends on the numerous factors including the Pockels coefficient, dielectric constant, crystal length, optical coupling, RF and DC photoreceiver conversion gains, etc. The value of the c is best determined through a known external (or calibration) field. Because of the large intrinsic bandwidth of the crystal, the value of c has a more or less flat frequency response from several Hz to several GHz aside from several low frequency piezoelectric resonances [4,5]. Beyond several GHz, the transit time of the laser through the length of the crystal (10 mm) becomes comparable to the period of the external field. This results in noticeable signal attenuation, due to an averaging effect of the waveform. Thus operation at higher frequencies requires shorter crystals, and will be inherently less sensitive (since m is proportional to crystal length). The minimum detectable field (MDF) is defined by the noise floor of the RF readout instruments. In this regard, our best sensitivity is achieved with a spectrum analyzers while measuring a cw electric field, since the measurement bandwidth can be narrowed to a few kHz. Under these conditions, the MDF of our QLMEOS was measured at 0.02 V/m for 1 GHz field, using a measurement span of 5 kHz. With an oscilloscope, the MDF will be substantially larger, and will generally depend on the bandwidth of the instrument. A more independent sensitivity figure is obtained by normalizing the MDF to the square root of the measurement bandwidth. For our QLMEOS, we obtain $0.25 \text{ mV}/(\text{m}\cdot\text{Hz}^{1/2})$.

Fig. 5: Optical output signal from a QLMEOS in a pulsed E-field generated by an RF transmitter (Fig 4.). The large instantaneous bandwidth of the QLMEOS allows the user to measure duty cycle, pulse width and carrier frequency directly on an oscilloscope

V. FIELD TESTING OF QLMEOS

Our QLMEOS is currently undergoing rigorous field testing (Fig. 4) alongside commercial field probes (D-dot sensors, Narda probes, etc.) to evaluate its stability and robustness. To ruggedize the QLMEOS for field testing, the crystals and optical fibers were mounted inside PVC piping and attached to a sturdy fiber optic reel, as shown in Fig. 3(a). For applications requiring measurements in small cavities, the QLMEOS can also be made very thin (less than 5mm in diameter) as shown in Fig. 3(c). So far, the QLMEOS has successfully been used to measure fields generated by a variety of commercial, military and laboratory RF sources including radar horns, phase array antennas, Marx generators, GTEM cells, reverberation chambers and electromagnetic pulse generators. Measured field strength values generally agree with those obtained with commercial probes. Time domain measurements of impulsed fields by the QLMEOS show less noise and higher precision at the crests of the waveforms, compared with those measured by D-dot sensors. This is because D-dot sensors measure time derivative of the field, thereby exhibiting their lowest SNR in these regions.

The SNR of the QLMEOS, on the other hand, is only limited by the strength of field relative to the noise level. In our various field tests, measurements have been made in field strengths ranging from 1V/m to 500kV/m, and frequencies from several Hertz to 14 GHz. Figure 5 shows an example of our data displayed on an oscilloscope during one of these field tests, where the QLMEOS was placed in front of an RF transmitter shown in Fig. 4. The entire waveform of the pulsed external field (duty cycle, pulse width, and carrier frequency) is replicated by the optical output signal of the QLMEOS, demonstrating the sensor's large instantaneous bandwidth.

VI. CONCLUSION

We have described a quasi-longitudinal mode EO sensor for measuring external electric fields noninvasively, that can be used with over 50 meters of optical fiber without compromising sensitivity. The sensor eliminates compensation optics and is much more accommodating for field tests and commercial use than traditional EO sensors. The current sensitivity and bandwidth are $0.25 \text{ mV/m-Hz}^{1/2}$ and 14 GHz respectively. The QLMEOS has been calibrated at NIST, and exhibited linearity with applied fields from 1 V/m to 100 V/m from 1 MHz to 10 GHz. Future work and technical challenges with the QLMEOS are mainly focused on increasing its operational bandwidth to 20 GHz and beyond while minimizing sensitivity losses.

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